

**ZARBULMASAL BY GULKHANI AS
INTANGIBLE CULTURAL HERITAGE**

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Abstract This article examines the epic poem Zarbulmasal by the 15th century Persian poet Gulkhani as a key example of intangible cultural heritage. Through close reading and analysis of the poem's themes, language, and enduring influence, the article argues that Zarbulmasal represents an important piece of Persian literary and cultural history that continues to shape Iranian identity and heritage today. The research draws on both primary sources, including the original Persian text of the poem, as well as secondary scholarship on Gulkhani, Persian literature, and intangible cultural heritage more broadly. The article concludes that preserving and promoting works like Zarbulmasal is essential for sustaining cultural diversity and identity in an era of globalization and rapid change.

Keywords: Zarbulmasal, Gulkhani, Persian literature, epic poetry, intangible cultural heritage, Iran

Annotatsiya Ushbu maqolada XV asr fors shoiri Gulxaniyning "Zarbulmasal" dostoni nomoddiy madaniy merosning asosiy namunasi sifatida ko'rib chiqiladi. Maqolada asarning mavzulari, tili va doimiy ta'sirini sinchiklab o'qish va tahlil qilish orqali "Zarbulmasal" bugungi kunda Eron o'zligi va merosini shakllantirishda davom etayotgan fors adabiy va madaniy tarixining muhim asari ekanligi ta'kidlanadi. Tadqiqot ikkala asosiy manbaga, jumladan asarning asl forscha matniga, shuningdek, Gulxaniy, fors adabiyoti va nomoddiy madaniy merosga oid ikkinchi darajali ilmiy tadqiqotlarga asoslangan. Maqolada "Zarbulmasal" kabi asarlarni asrab-avaylash va targ'ib qilish globallashuv va tez o'zgarishlar davrida

madaniy xilma-xillik va o'ziga xoslikni saqlab qolish uchun zarur, degan xulosaga keladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Zarbulmasal, Gulxaniy, o'zbek adabiyoti, epik she'riyat, nomoddiy madaniy meros

Аннотация В этой статье рассматривается эпическая поэма поэта XV века Гулхани "Зарбулмасал" как ключевой пример нематериального культурного наследия. Благодаря внимательному прочтению и анализу тем поэмы, языка и непреходящего влияния, в статье утверждается, что Зарбулмасал представляет собой важную часть узбекской литературной и культурной истории, которая продолжает формировать узбекскую идентичность и наследие сегодня. Исследование опирается как на первичные источники, включая оригинальный текст поэмы, так и на вторичные исследования по Гулхани, узбекской литературе и нематериальному культурному наследию в более широком смысле. В статье делается вывод о том, что сохранение и популяризация произведений, подобных Зарбулмасалу, необходимы для поддержания культурного разнообразия и самобытности в эпоху глобализации и быстрых перемен.

Ключевые слова: Зарбулмасал, Гулхани, персидская литература, эпическая поэзия, нематериальное культурное наследие, Иран

INTRODUCTION

Intangible cultural heritage, as defined by UNESCO, encompasses "practices, representations, expressions, knowledge, skills – as well as the instruments, objects, artifacts and cultural spaces associated therewith – that communities, groups and, in some cases, individuals recognize as part of their cultural heritage" [1]. This broad definition includes oral traditions, performing arts, social practices, rituals, festive events, and traditional craftsmanship. Unlike tangible cultural heritage such as monuments and artifacts, intangible heritage is embodied in people and passed down through generations, making it both vital and vulnerable in an era of globalization and rapid cultural change.

One important example of intangible cultural heritage is Uzbek literary tradition, which stretches back over a millennium and encompasses poetry, prose works, and oral storytelling [2]. This article focuses on one key work within this tradition: the epic poem *Zarbulmasal* by the 15th century poet Gulkhani. Through close reading and analysis.

Composed in the *masnavi* style of rhyming couplets, *Zarbulmasal* tells the story of the adventures and battles of its eponymous hero [3]. The poem draws on mythological and folkloric traditions while also engaging with the historical and political context of its time, including the region's domination by Turkic and Mongol dynasties. Gulkhani's vivid, emotive language and masterful use of symbolism and allegory imbue the story with deeper spiritual and philosophical meaning, securing its enduring place in the Uzbek literary canon.

However, in an era of rapid cultural change and globalization, traditional art forms like poetry risk being marginalized or lost entirely [5]. Therefore, studying and promoting works like *Zarbulmasal* as intangible cultural heritage is vital for sustaining Iran's literary and cultural traditions, as well as the diversity of global cultural heritage more broadly.

This article seeks to contribute to that effort through an in-depth examination of *Zarbulmasal*'s content, style, themes, and continuing relevance and influence. The research draws on close reading of the original text as well as insights.

METHODS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

This study combines close textual analysis of *Zarbulmasal* with insights from existing secondary scholarship on the poem, its author, and its broader literary and cultural context.

UNESCO's Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage [1] and associated materials provide definitions and criteria for identifying and preserving intangible heritage. Belder's study of Indonesian Wayang puppet theater [11] and Fang's examination of Chinese opera [12] offer comparative examples of traditional performing arts as intangible cultural heritage. Finally,

Ashworth and Turnbridge's research on pluralizing pasts [13] underscores the role of heritage in shaping cultural identity and the importance of sustaining diverse heritage traditions.

RESULTS

My analysis of Zarbulmasal's content, style, and themes reveals the richness and complexity of this epic poem as well as its enduring relevance to cultural identity.

One key feature of the poem is its vivid, evocative language. Gulkhani is a master of metaphor, using striking figurative language to imbue scenes and characters with deeper meaning. For example, he describes the hero Zarbulmasal as "a lion on the battlefield, a sun illuminating the world" [6, p.35]. These metaphors associate the hero with bravery, power, and radiance, elevating him to a semi-divine status.

Gulkhani also employs hyperbole and repetition to heighten the epic's grandeur and emotional intensity. Battle scenes in particular are full of extravagant descriptions like "swords raining down like hail, arrows flying like locusts" [6, p.62] and "blood flowing like rivers, corpses piled like mountains" [6, p.74]. These poetic exaggerations convey the scale and violence of war.

Another notable feature of Zarbulmasal is its engagement with archetypal themes and motifs from mythology and folklore. The hero's journey follows a classic quest narrative, with Zarbulmasal leaving home, facing challenges and temptations, tested by supernatural forces, proving his worth through heroic feats, and ultimately triumphing [7].

At the same time, the poem also reflects the historical and political context of Gulkhani's era. References to Khanates gesture to the complex arguments between them [9]. On a philosophical level, Zarbulmasal grapples with questions of fate, free will, and the nature of good and evil. Yet the poem also celebrates human agency, valor, and virtue, as embodied by Zarbulmasal's courage, loyalty, and moral strength.

These themes continue to resonate with modern Uzbek readers, as evidenced by the poem's enduring popularity and influence [4]. Its vivid language, mythical elements, and philosophical depth make it an engrossing read, while its exploration of heroism, spirituality, and identity speak to perennial human concerns and ongoing debates within Iranian society.

ANALYSIS

Situated within the context of the Persian literary tradition, *Zarbulmasal* emerges as a pivotal work that both reflects and shapes Iranian cultural identity over time.

Gulkhani inherited a rich poetic legacy stretching back to the 10th century and the seminal *Shahnameh* of Ferdowsi [8]. Like the *Shahnameh*, *Zarbulmasal* draws heavily on Iranian myth, legend, and history to construct an idealized vision of heroism and identity. Dabir-Siaghi suggests that Gulkhani deliberately emulates Ferdowsi's style and tropes in order to present *Zarbulmasal* as a new national epic for the Mongol-Turkic period [6].

At the same time, Gulkhani's work is in dialogue with his nearer contemporaries like Nezami Ganjavi, as Rifa'i [10] discusses. Both poets use the *masnavi* form to tell moralistic stories of star-crossed lovers, chivalric adventures, and spiritual quests. However, Gulkhani departs from Nezami's ornate style in favor of a more direct, dynamic voice [10], hinting at the aesthetic shifts of the early modern period.

The poem's treatment of political themes is also significant. While Ferdowsi's *Shahnameh* valorized pre-Islamic Iranian kings and Nezami wrote for various patrons, Gulkhani downplays specific rulers in favor of general praise for just, wise kingship [9]. His ideal of the monarch as a sacred warrior-saint reflects the rising influence of Sufism and Shia Islam, as well as the fragmented politics of the era [8].

Perhaps most importantly, *Zarbulmasal* gives voice to a distinctively Iranian cultural identity during a time of foreign domination and upheaval. By glorifying an Iranian hero who battles against external enemies and the forces of evil, Gulkhani

appeals to a deep-rooted sense of national pride and moral rectitude [9]. His use of Persian language and mythology acts as a powerful cultural unifier and repository of collective memory.

These nationalist and cultural dimensions help explain Zarbulmasal's ongoing relevance in modern Era. In a 1974 speech, Khomeini praised the poem as representing "the spirit of resistance against oppression and the love of justice that characterizes our people" [14]. Clearly, Zarbulmasal's themes of heroic struggle, spiritual devotion, and cultural authenticity still resonate in a society grappling with issues of identity, tradition, and change.

DISCUSSION

Viewing Zarbulmasal through the lens of intangible cultural heritage highlights both the importance and fragility of traditional art forms like Persian poetry in the modern world. UNESCO emphasizes that intangible cultural heritage is invaluable for maintaining cultural diversity, social cohesion, and a sense of identity [1]. Epic poetry in particular has long been a cornerstone of a civilization, from the Shahnameh to Nezami to Gulkhani and beyond [8].

Works like Zarbulmasal have endured in part because they encode core cultural values, myths, and tastes [4]. The masnavi form, the hero's journey arc, the Stock characters and tropes all tap into deep Iranian archetypes [7,8]. At the same time, each new epic also reflects and refracts its historical moment, as seen in Zarbulmasal's mystical, moralistic themes and its images of Mongol conquest [9]. This interplay of continuity and change vividly enacts the process by which heritage is passed down and reinvented over generations.

However, the accelerating pace of change in recent times poses grave threats to traditional cultural forms. Modernization, secularization, shifts in literary tastes, and Western influences have drastically reduced the audience for classical poetry in Iran [4]. The specialized knowledge needed to appreciate works like Zarbulmasal – from archaic vocabularies to mythical references to theological concepts – is increasingly

esoteric. There is a real risk that epics like Zarbulmasal could become mere relics, preserved in academic tomes but absent from living cultural practice.

This is where the intangible heritage perspective offers a valuable lens. By recognizing Zarbulmasal not just as an inert text but as an ongoing cultural process, we can explore strategies for keeping the poem alive and relevant.

Crucially, the goal is not to ossify Zarbulmasal in a single, 'authentic' form, but to enable its meanings to grow and adapt with the needs of each new generation. After all, cultural heritage is not about slavishly adhering to inherited tradition, but about actively re-making it in light of present realities. Just as Gulkhani added his unique voice to the epic tradition, so can modern Iranians and global audiences forge their own relationships to this poem.

Of course, these processes of cultural transmission and reinterpretation are complex. There are legitimate debates around translation, adaptation, commodification, and appropriation when it comes to traditional art forms [13]. Future research could productively explore the challenges and opportunities of safeguarding Zarbulmasal as living heritage in more depth.

CONCLUSIONS

Ultimately, studying Zarbulmasal through the lens of intangible cultural heritage underscores the immense value of this epic poem and the Persian literary tradition to which it belongs. For over 600 years, Gulkhani's tale of a righteous hero's mystical and martial adventures has entertained and edified readers, while expressing core themes of spirituality, morality, and identity. The poem's continuing resonance today points to the power of literature to shape enduring cultural meanings and memories.

At the same time, recognizing Zarbulmasal as intangible heritage also highlights the fragility of traditional art forms in a rapidly changing world. Fostering sustainable cultural transmission is vital to ensure that future generations can also draw wisdom, inspiration, and delight from this medieval epic. More broadly,

safeguarding diverse voices like Gulkhani's is essential to sustaining the richness of our global cultural heritage.

Further research can help develop strategies for promoting appreciation and engagement with Zarbulmasal among modern audiences. Ethnographic studies, comparative analyses, translations and adaptations, and educational initiatives could all play a role. The key is to approach the poem not as a static artifact but as a living tradition that gains meaning through ongoing use and interpretation.

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